

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI FANLAR AKADEMIYASI
MINTAQAVIY BO‘LIMI
XORAZM MA‘MUN AKADEMIYASI**

**XORAZM MA‘MUN
AKADEMIYASI
AXBOROTNOMASI**

Axborotnoma OAK Rayosatining 2016-yil 29-dekabrdagi 223/4-son qarori bilan biologiya, qishloq xo‘jaligi, tarix, iqtisodiyot, filologiya va arxitektura fanlari bo‘yicha doktorlik dissertatsiyalari asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etish tavsiya etilgan ilmiy nashrlar ro‘yxatiga kiritilgan

2025-4/4

**Xorazm Ma‘mun akademiyasi axborotnomasi
2006 yildan boshlab chop qilinadi**

Xiva-2025

Bosh muharrir:*Abdullayev Ikram Iskandarovich, b.f.d., prof.***Bosh muharrir o‘rinbosari:***Hasanov Shodlik Bekpo‘latovich, k.f.n., k.i.x.***Tahrir hayati:**

Abdullayev Ikram Iskandarovich, b.f.d., prof.
Abdullayeva Muborak Maxmusovna, b.f.d., prof.
Abduhalimov Bahrom Abduraximovich, t.f.d., prof.
Agzamova Gulchexra Azizovna, t.f.d., prof.
Aimbetov Nagmet Kalliyevich, i.f.d., akad.
Ametov Yakub Idrisovich, b.f.d., prof.
Babadjanov Xushnut, f.f.n., prof.
Bahodirova Feruza Bahodir qizi, PhD, dots,
Bobojonova Sayyora Xushnudovna, b.f.n., dos.
Bekchanov Davron Jumanazarovich, k.f.d.
Buriyev Xasan Chutbayevich, b.f.d., prof.
Gandjayeva Lola Atanazarovna, b.f.d., k.i.x.
Davletov Sanjar Rajabovich, tar.f.d.
Durdiyeva Gavhar Salayevna, arx.f.d.
Ibragimov Baxtiyor To‘laganovich, k.f.d., akad.
Izzatullayev Zuvayd, b.f.d., prof.
Ismailov Is‘haqjon Otabayevich, f.f.n., dos.
Jumaniyozov Otaboy, f.f.d., prof.
Jumaniyozov Zoxid Otaboyevich, f.f.n., dos.
Jumanov Murat Arepbayevich, b.f.d., prof.
Kadirova Shaxnoza Abduxalilovna, k.f.d., prof.
Qalandarov Nazimxon Nazirovich, b.f.f.d., k.i.x.
Karabayev Ikramjan Turayevich, q/x.f.d., prof.
Karimov Ulug‘bek Temirbayevich, DSc
Kurbanbayev Ilhom Jumanazarovich, b.f.d., prof.
Kurbanova Saida Bekchanovna, f.f.n., dos.
Qutliyev Uchqun Otaboyevich, f-m.f.d., prof.
Lamers Jon, q/x.f.d., prof.
Maykl S. Enjel, b.f.d., prof.
Maxmudov Raufjon Baxodirovich, f.f.d., k.i.x.
Mirzayev Sirojiddin Zayniyevich, f-m.f.d., prof.
Matniyozova Hilola Xudoyberganovna, b.f.d., prof.
Masharipova Feruza Jumanazarovna, PhD

Mirzayeva Gulnara Saidarifovna, b.f.d.
Najmeddinov Axmad Raxmatovich PhD, dotsent
Pazilov Abdvayeit, b.f.d., prof.
Razzaqova Surayyo Razzoqovna, k.f.f.d., dos.
Ramatov Bakmat Zaripovich, q/x.f.n., dos.
Raximov Raxim Atajanovich, t.f.d., prof.
Raximov Matnazar Shomurotovich, b.f.d., prof.
Raximova Go‘zal Yuldashovna, f.f.f.d., dos.
Ro‘zmetov Baxtiyar, i.f.d., prof.
Ro‘zmetov Dilshod Ro‘zimboyevich, g.f.n., k.i.x.
Ruzmetov Davron Ibrogimovich, PhD
Sadullayev Azimboy, f-m.f.d., akad.
Salayev San‘atbek Komilovich, i.f.d., prof.
Saparbayeva Gulandam Masharipovna, f.f.f.d.
Saparov Kalandar Abdullayevich, b.f.d., prof.
Safarov Alisher Karimdjaniyevich, b.f.d., dos.
Sirojov Oybek Ochilovich, s.f.d., prof.
Sobitov O‘lmasboy Tojxmedovich, b.f.f.d., k.i.x.
Sotipov Goyipnazar, q/x.f.d., prof.
Tojibayev Komiljon Sharobitdinovich, b.f.d., akad.
Xolliyev Askar Ergashevich, b.f.d., prof.
Xolmatov Baxtiyor Rustamovich, b.f.d.
Cho‘ponov Otanazar Otojonovich, f.f.d., dos.
Shakarboyev Erkin Berdikulovich, b.f.d., prof.
Ermatova Jamila Ismailovna, f.f.n., dos.
Eshchanov Ruzumboy Abdullayevich, b.f.d., prof.
O‘razboyev G‘ayrat O‘razaliyevich, f-m.f.d.
O‘rozboyev Abdulla Durdiyevich, f.f.d.
Hajiyeva Maqsuda Sultonovna, fal.f.d.
Hasanov Shodlik Bekpo‘latovich, k.f.n., k.i.x.
Xudayberganova Durdona Sidiqovna, f.f.d.
Yuldashev Xamza Kamalovich, PhD
Zaripova Ranojon Zaripovna, PhD, dotsent

Xorazm Ma‘mun akademiyasi axborotnomasi: ilmiy jurnal.-№4/4 (125), Xorazm Ma‘mun akademiyasi, 2025 y. – 263 b. – Bosma nashrning elektron varianti - <https://www.mamun.uz/bulletin>

ISSN 2091-573 X

Muassis: O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasi mintaqaviy bo‘limi – Xorazm Ma‘mun akademiyasi

© Xorazm Ma‘mun akademiyasi noshirlik bo‘limi, 2025

MUNDARIJA
FILOLOGIYA FANLARI

Abdullayeva F.B. Koreys roman janri taraqqiyotida adibalarning tutgan o‘rni	6
Abduqaxarov Q.A. Ingliz va o‘zbek tilida urg‘u va ohangning pragmatik xususiyatlari	10
Abdusalimov S.R. Jon Ronald Tolkinning ingliz adabiyotida fantastik janrdagi ijodi	13
Abdushukurova G.A. Stilistik uslub va yozuvchining individual yondashuvi	15
Abiyatova M.M. Differences between machine translation and human translation: a comparative study of “The little prince”	18
Akindikov N.B. Selection and theoretical philological criteria in the promotion of enlightenment ideas in school literary studies	21
Alibekova M.A. Beyond the basics: elevating pragmatics in the uzbek high school context	24
Allayev Z.M. Linguistic aspects of oneirosphere: a comparative analysis	27
Alxiyeva S.R. “Tabiatning ikkinchi siri” afsonasining tahlili va talqini	29
Amirqulova N. Fraseologizmlar tarkibida qo‘shma so‘zlar derivatsiyasi va struktur semantik ko‘chimlar	33
Anarboyeva I.O. Nominativ birliklarning gender tamoyillari xususida	35
Arifova U.A. Tarjimashunoslikda ekvivalentsiz leksika borasidagi nazariy qarashlar	39
Ashurov B.Sh. Linguistic markers of speech manipulation in forensic analysis of english and uzbek languages	42
Atamurodova F.T. Roman trilogiya janri va Joys Keri trilogiyasining badiiy xususiyatlari	44
Axmadjonov I. Dunyo tilshunosligida morfem birliklar haqida qarashlarning shakllanishi	47
Axmedov J.G’. Linguistic landcape of fire and water: analyzing idioms and proverbs in uzbek and english	50
Axrarova G.X. Antonim so‘zlarning she‘riy misralarda qo‘llanilishi	52
Axunova M.A., O‘rmonova M.F. Ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida miqdor konseptiga oid neologizmlar	55
Azimova S.A. “Yosh” konsepti asosida madaniy-pragmatik qadriyatlarning lingvistik talqini	60
Azizova M.B. Ibora va gap ko‘rinishida uchrovchi epitetlarning o‘zbek tiliga tarjimasini tamoyillari	63
Barotova N.Sh. Olamning lisoniy manzarasini hosil qilishda qo‘llaniladigan lisoniy hamda nolisoniy omillar tahlili	66
Begmatova S.B. Adabiyot olamida romantizm yo‘nalishdagi ijod qilgan adiblar	70
Bobokalonov R.O. Fransuz va o‘zbek tibbiyot terminologiyasining tarixiy rivojlanishi	73
Boboqulova G.Sh. Badiiy tarjimada muammolar va yechimlar	78
Boltabayeva M.B. Grem Grinning diniy qarashlarini “Kuch va shon-shuhrat” romanida aks ettirilishi	81
Boltayeva D.Sh. The transformative power of the novella in literature and society	83
Botirova N.F. Chikano – mojarro va kurash she‘riyati	86
Boymurodova G.M. Ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida mehnat mazmunli maqollarning yasashida grammatik tuzilish	89
Bozorova M.U. Mediadiskursda til shaxsiyati va uning pragmatolingvistik tadqiqi	91
Burieva U.A. Analysis of incomplete sentences in discourse in uzbek and english	94
Burxonova M.M. Nolisoniy tizim tasnifiga doir	97
Choriyeva Ch.S. Turg‘unlashuviga ko‘ra diniy leksika	99
Davletova I.U., Jumaniyazova D.A. Ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida oddiy, qiyosiy va orttirma darajali sifat komponentli frazeologizmlar	102
Djumaeva N.D., Bakhshilloeva N.I. Linguistic features of the concept of “magic” in english and uzbek cultures: a comparative-cognitive analysis	105
Djumayeva N., Abduxolikova A. “O‘tkan kunlar” romanida inson ruhiy holatini ifodalovchi lisoniy birliklar tahlili	108
Djumayeva N., Sultanmuradova D. Pragmatic features of infinitive and infinitive constructions	110
Egamberdiyev J.J. O‘zbek tili izohli lug‘atlarida terminlarning kodifikatsiya qilinishi	113

Ergashev M.B. Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida muhabbat izhorini ifodalashda pragmatik yondashuv	116
Ergasheva G.Sh. O'zbek tilida do'stlik/dushmanlik konseptlarini ifodalovchi maqollar	120
Ergasheva N.E. Structural and semantic characteristics of names of culinary products in english-language discourse	123
Ergasheva N.K. Developing social and emotional skills alongside language skills	126
Eshboltayev B.J. Bolalar reklama matnlarini shakllantirish tamoyillari	128
Eshonqulova S.I. Nodira she'riyatida diniy-ma'rifiy va falsafiy-tasavvufiy qarashlar talqini	131
Eshpulatova O'.G'. Tarjima jarayonida badiiy vositalarning o'ziga xosliklarini saqlash masalasi	134
Fayzullayeva N.S. Tilning morfologik darajasida so'z tuzilishini soddalashtirishga intilishi tejamkorlik tamoyili doirasida tahlili	136
Gadayeva M.M. Cho'lponning she'rlarida erk, ozodlik va o'zlik masalalari	140
Gafurov B.Z. Organization and self-organization of text as a "living system"	143
G'ofurova N.M., Ganiyeva D.A. Exploring metaphor and simile: insights from uzbek and english texts	147
Haydarov A.A., Sattorova Sh. Punktuatsion va turli ishora belgilari orqali ifodalangan konnotativ ma'nolar	149
Hayitov Sh.A., Barotova X.J. "Boburnoma"da zuhrabegi og'a tasviri	152
Hidayatova A.T. Yan Kvi Ja hikoyalarida ota obrazining o'rni	155
Ibodullayeva Sh.D., Mirzakulova N.G. Vocabulary matters: integrating meaning, use, and memory. Focus on arabic	158
Ibragimova G.M. Abbreviaturalar til oshiqchaligi va tejamkorligini yuzaga keltiruvchi omil sifatida	161
Iskandarova G.M., Khalbayeva M.U., Saparbaeva G.M. Theoretical trends on the classification of the english phrases	164
Ismailov I.O. Ogahiy solnomalari badiiyatini yuzaga keltirishda mumtoz asarlar uslub va ruhiyati ta'siri masalasi	168
Ismailov I.O. Ogahiy tarixiy-adabiy asarlari badiiyatini yuzaga keltirishda firdavsiyning roli	173
Ismailova Kh.N. The evolution of style and form in literary influence	176
Ismoilova Sh. The evolution and history of english language	180
Jalolova M.B. Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida kesatiqning verbal va noverbal ifoda vositalari	183
Jo'rayev J.A. "Abushqa" va "Gulshan ul-asror" qo'lyozma nusxalari matnining qiyosiy tahlili	187
Jomardova D.Q. O'zbek va rus tillari tibbiyot reklama matnlarida aks etgan apellyativ leksikaning lingvomadaniy jihatlarida individuallik va o'xshashliklar	190
Jumaniyazova M.A. Linguacultural evolution of proverbs and fables in english and uzbek proverbs	193
Jumanyazova M.X. Xorazm vohasi folklori tilidagi shaxs ma'naviyatini ifodalovchi til birliklari xususida	196
Karimboyeva S., Isxokov B. Yoshlarni vatanga muhabbat ruhida tarbiyalashda tarix fanining roli	199
Karimov R.K. Terminologiya sohasining tilshunoslikdagi o'rni	201
Karimova M.S. The importance of gender roles in ordinary discourse	204
Karshiyeva T.I. Transcendentalism and jadid literature: a comparison of views on understanding nature, humanity, and freedom	206
Khudayberganova N.R. Maqol janriga xos ayrim xususiyatlar haqida	210
Kobilova N.S., Azimova M.Sh. Evaluative units in the english language and their pragmatic features	215
Kobilova N.S., Yusupova D.T. Phonetic economy in the english language: epenthesis, diaeresis, metathesis as derivatives of assimilation and dissimilation	218
Komilova D.M. Abdulla Qahhorning "Dahshat" hikoyasida shamol detali orqali "qo'rquv" semasining aktuallashuvi	219

Kosimova M.U. O'zbek va ingliz tillarida ish hujjatlari matnining izomorf va allomorf jihatlarini hamda tarjima masalalari	222
Kudratova M.K. The aspects of appearing and forming retronyms in language	224
Kurbanova B.K. Xorazm dostonlari tili leksikasini o'rganish ahamiyati	227
Mamaniyozov H.T. O'zbek va nemis tillarida paremiologik materiallar, xalq og'zaki ijodi, folkloristik manbalar	230
Mamatkulova O. Improving the competence of professors and problems of learning languages by using ICT	233
Melikova G.T. Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida "oila tarbiyasi"ga oid leksik birliklarning o'zaro ma'no aloqalari va ko'p ma'nolilikni tahlil qilishning kognitiv modeli	235
Mirzatillayeva Z.R., Aliyeva N.X. Olamning lisoniy manzarasi lingvistik bilim tizimida	238
Mirzayev X.T. "Muntaxab ul-aruz" risolasida aruz bahrlari tasnifi	240
Movlanova R. Bridging cultures in global finance: ensuring translational equivalence in international financial documentation	243
Muratova G.Ch. G'afur G'ulom ijodida obraz masalalari	247
Murtazayev E.N. The imagination and interpretation of warriors in heroic epics	249
Murtozayeva N.J. Socio-historical basis of Ernest Hemingway's "A farewell to arms"	252
Muslixiddinova R. Til o'rganish jarayonining neyrolingvistik tahlili	254
Muxammadiyeva Sh.A. Ingliz va o'zbek badiiy matnlarida estetik baho omilining lingvomadaniy xususiyatlari	257
Muxammadiyeva Sh.A. Ingliz va o'zbek badiiy matnlarida estetik baho omilining lingvomadaniy xususiyatlari	260

3. Garzone, G. (2000). Legal translation and functionalist approaches: A contradiction in terms? In L. Gotti & M. Dossena (Eds.), *Legal Language in Use: Translation, Terminology, Drafting and Procedural Issues* (pp. 395–414). Peter Lang.
4. House, J. (2015). *Translation Quality Assessment: Past and Present* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
5. Munday, J. (2016). *Introducing Translation Studies: Theories and Applications* (4th ed.). Routledge.
6. Newmark, P. (1988). *A Textbook of Translation*. Prentice Hall.
7. Nord, C. (2005). *Text Analysis in Translation: Theory, Methodology, and Didactic Application of a Model for Translation-Oriented Text Analysis*. Rodopi.
8. Šarčević, S. (2000). *New Approach to Legal Translation*. Kluwer Law International.
9. Trosborg, A. (1997). *Text Typology and Translation*. John Benjamins.
10. Wagner, E., Bech, S., & Martínez, J. M. (2002). *Translating for the European Union Institutions*. Manchester: St. Jerome Publishing.
11. Venuti, L. (2012). *The Translator's Invisibility: A History of Translation* (2nd ed.). Routledge.

UO`K 81-13

G`AFUR G`ULOM IJODIDA OBRAZ MASALALARI

G.Ch.Muratova, mustaqil tadqiqotchi, Nukus davlat pedagogika institute, Nukus

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada G`afur G`ulomning badiiy ijodida obraz yaratishning o`ziga xos xususiyatlari tahlil etiladi. Adibning lirik “men”i, otalik obrazini shakllantirishdagi noan’anaviy yondashuvi, an’anaviy timsollarga bergan zamonaviy talqini, shuningdek, ruhiy-kechinmaviy holatlarning poetik ifodasi ilmiy asosda yoritiladi. Tadqiqot davomida G`afur G`ulomning poeziyasida lirik qahramon ichki olamining obraz orqali ochib berilishi, shoir qo`llagan badiiy usullar va ularning ma`naviy-estetik yuklamasi tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so`zlar: obraz, lirik “men”, otalik timsoli, badiiy tasvir, poetik mahorat, ruhiy kechinma, zamonaviy talqin, timsol, poetik fikrlash, lirik qahramon.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются особенности создания образа в творчестве Гафура Гулама. На научной основе исследуются лирическое «я» писателя, его нетрадиционный подход к формированию образа отцовства, современная интерпретация им традиционных символов, а также поэтическое выражение эмоциональных состояний. В исследовании анализируется раскрытие внутреннего мира лирического героя через образы в поэзии Гафура Гулама, художественные приемы, используемые поэтом, их духовно-эстетическое значение.

Ключевые слова: образ, лирическое «Я», отцовство, художественный образ, поэтическое мастерство, духовный опыт, современная интерпретация, символ, поэтическое мышление, лирический герой.

Abstract. This article analyzes the specific features of image creation in Gafur Gulom's artistic work. The writer's lyrical "I", his unconventional approach to forming the image of fatherhood, his modern interpretation of traditional symbols, as well as the poetic expression of emotional states are scientifically covered. During the research, the disclosure of the inner world of the lyrical hero through the image in Gafur Gulom's poetry, the artistic methods used by the poet and their spiritual and aesthetic load are analyzed.

Keywords: image, lyrical "I", image of fatherhood, artistic image, poetic skill, emotional experience, modern interpretation, symbol, poetic thinking, lyrical hero.

Kirish. O`zbek adabiyotida G`afur G`ulom siymosi o`ziga xos ijodiy maktabni yaratgan adib sifatida e`tirof etiladi. Shoirning badiiy tafakkuri, g`oyaviy pozitsiyasi, lirik “men”ining boyligi va ruhiy kechinmalarning obrazlar vositasida ifoda etilishi uning she`riyati va nasriyati asosini tashkil etadi. Ayniqsa, adib tomonidan yaratilgan otalik, mehnatkash, vatanparvar obrazlari milliy timsollar galereyasida alohida o`rin egallaydi. Obrazlar adabiy ijodda inson ruhiyati, jamiyatdagi o`zgarishlar va davr talablarini ifodalashda asosiy vositadir. G`afur G`ulom mumtoz adabiy an`analardan ilhomlangan holda, o`z davrining estetik tamoyillariga tayangan, biroq ularga zamonaviy talqin bergan ijodkordir. Ayniqsa, uning “Sog`inish”, “Kuzatish” kabi lirik she`rlari, “Qish” she`ri orqali berilgan allegorik-patriotik obrazlar va badiiy tamsillar obrazga falsafiy yuklama berish mahoratini yaqqol namoyon etadi. Shoirning badiiy timsollari akademik va murakkab ramzlardan ko`ra, xalqona

ifodalar, oddiy hayotiy obrazlar asosida quriladi. Bu obrazlar murakkablikdan emas, aksincha, soddalikdan, hayot bilan bog'liq real tajribalardan kuch oladi. Masalan, "Qish" she'rida fasl timsolida sovuq, qahraton, lekin chidamli mehnatkash hayoti tasvirlanadi. Qish bu yerda faqat fasl emas, balki jamiyatdagi og'irliklar, sinovlar timsolidir. Timsol xalq uchun tushunarli bo'lib, chuqur ma'naviy asosga ega.

Adabiyotlar sharhi. G'afur G'ulomning lirik she'riyatida obraz — bu shunchaki poetik timsol emas, balki ichki kechinma, ruhiy holat, muayyan davr ijtimoiy ziddiyatlarining badiiy aksidir. Shoir ko'proq ichki "men"ga, ruhiy olamga yuzlanadi. Masalan, "Ota" she'rida lirik qahramon otasining hayoti orqali mehnatga sadoqat, fidoiylilik, qashshoqlikdagi g'urur va ichki matonat obrazini yaratadi. Bu obrazda otaning siymosi vaqtlar, toifadagi bir inson emas — butun bir avlodning, tarixiy jarayonning badiiy ifodasi sifatida talqin qilinadi [1].

Shoir timsollarni yaratishda tazod, ruhiy keskinlik, ichki monolog kabi vositalarga tayangan. Bunda obraz abstraktlikdan yiroq, balki hayotiy, jonli va sezgir tilda ifodalanadi. Masalan, "Kuzatish" she'rida obraz faqatgina kuzatuvchi emas, balki jamiyatning o'tmish va kelajagiga nigoh tashlaydigan, unda ichki e'tiroz, sog'inch, umid birlashgan timsoldir. G'afur G'ulom faqat she'riyatda emas, balki nasrda ham obrazlar yaratish orqali zamonaviy insonning ichki dunyosini, jamiyatdagi o'zgarishlarga munosabatini ifodalaydi. Uning "Shum bola" asaridagi asosiy qahramon bolaning sho'xligi, ayni paytda samimiyligi, dunyoni o'zgartirishga intilayotgan g'ayrati orqali xalq orasidagi odatiy, biroq chuqur insoniy obrazlar aks ettiriladi.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi va empirik tahlil. Shoir ko'p hollarda konkret shaxs timsolida umumxalq holatini tasvirlaydi. Bu uslubiy yondashuvda obraz ijtimoiy sathga ko'tariladi va umumlashma kuchini oladi. "So'z" she'rida esa obraz timsollar orqali emas, balki poetik fikrning o'zida mujassam: so'z — qudrat, mas'uliyat, harakatning yetakchisi sifatida aks ettiriladi. Bu yerda obraz tilda emas, falsafada namoyon bo'ladi. G'afur G'ulom obrazlarni shakllantirishda badiiy til imkoniyatlaridan mahorat bilan foydalangan. Efitetlar, metaforalar, badiiy tazodlar, ritmik o'yinlar orqali obrazlar yanada jonli, tasirchan tus oladi. Misol uchun, "Sog'inish" she'rida "onang ko'zlari soyabonday..." ifodasi bilan onaning timsoli nafaqat jismonan, balki ruhiy panoh sifatida tasvirlanadi. Bu orqali lirik obrazning ichki tuyg'ulari va hissiy zaminini chuqurroq ochib beradi.

Shoirning tilidagi soddalik, obrazdagi murakkablik bilan uyg'unlashgan holda lirik to'qimalarni realistik ruhda boyitadi. Bu jihat G'afur G'ulom obrazlari vaqt va makon bilan cheklanmagan, balki har bir avlod uchun o'z ruhiy mujassami sifatida yashay olishini anglatadi [2].

Natijalar. G'afur G'ulom ijodining muhim xususiyatlaridan biri — obrazning tashqi xususiyatlaridan ko'ra, uning ichki dunyosini ochishga intilishdir. Shoir lirik qahramon ruhiyatini tahlil qilishda so'z san'atining badiiy qudratidan to'liq foydalanadi. Ayniqsa, "Sog'indim seni, onajon" she'rida lirik qahramon hissiyotlari, ichki bo'shliq, yolg'izlik va mehrga tashnalik she'r obrazining ruhiy asosiga aylangan.

Bu obrazlar yordamida shoir o'quvchini ham kechinmalarga sherik qiladi, uni hissiy jihatdan obraz bilan bog'laydi. Bu jihat G'afur G'ulom obrazlarining yuqori darajada psixologik yuksaklikka ega ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

G'afur G'ulom lirik she'riyatida "men" ko'pincha umumlashgan xalqiy "men"ga aylanadi. Bu jihat uning lirik qahramonini individual kechinmalar ifodachisidan ko'ra, milliy ruh va zamon kechinmalarining vakiliga aylantiradi.

Manbalarda ta'kidlanishicha, G'afur G'ulom o'z she'rlarida o'z davrining ziddiyatlarini "men" orqali bergan. U ruhiy halovat, hayotdagi ezgulik, onalik mehrini aynan lirik obrazlar vositasida xalq ichiga olib kiradi. Bu "men" ba'zan bolalik, ba'zan otalik, ba'zan esa ona ruhi bilan bog'langan shaklda namoyon bo'ladi.

Shoir yaratgan obrazlar bir yoqlama emas, balki ko'p qatlamli semantik yuklamaga ega. Masalan, "So'z" she'rida so'z — bu aloqa vositasi emas, balki axloqiy javobgarlik, jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy pozitsiya va shaxsiy vijdonning timsoli bo'lib chiqadi. Bu obraz ko'rinishidan soddadir, ammo mazmun jihatidan murakkab ijtimoiy-falsafiy tushunchalarni o'z ichiga oladi [3].

G'afur G'ulom obrazlari orqali o'zbek xalqining mentaliteti, axloqiy ideallari va ma'naviy qadriyatlarini ifodalanadi. Uning qahramonlari, avvalo, ichki poklik, mehnatsevarlik, sabr-toqat,

e'tiqod va mehr bilan ajralib turadi. Masalan, "Ona tili" she'rida ona tili obrazini millat ruhi, madaniy meros va ajdodlar xotirasi sifatida talqin etadi. Bu timsol xalq uchun yaqin, tanish va yurakka ta'sirchan tarzda beriladi.

Shoirning obrazlari orqali o'zbek millatiga xos xarakter — kamtarlik, or-nomus, vatanparvarlik badiiy vositalar orqali ifodalangan. Bu jihatlari G'afur G'ulom poetikasining asosiy ma'naviy yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida baholanishi mumkin.

G'afur G'ulom obrazlarida kontrast — qarama-qarshi his-tuyg'ular, shartlar va voqealarning badiiy taqqoslanishi orqali lirik qahramon xarakteri ochiladi. Ayniqsa, "Men va sen" she'rida "men" va "sen" qarama-qarshi kuchlar sifatida talqin qilinadi: biri inkor, biri e'tirof, biri shubha, biri ishonch. Bu usul orqali shoir faqat bir holatni emas, balki jarayonni, ichki o'zgarishni, kechinma dinamikasini aks ettiradi.

Shu tarzda G'afur G'ulom obrazlari faqat bir qarashda emas, balki tafakkur jarayonida tobora ochilib boradigan badiiy struktura kasb etadi. Ular o'quvchini fikrlashga, his qilishga undaydi [4].

G'afur G'ulom obrazlari ko'pincha muayyan bir tarixiy davrning badiiy aksidir. Shoir faqat inson obrazini emas, balki davrni, vaqtni, muhitni timsollashtiradi. Uning "Ketmonchi" yoki "Mehnat" singari asarlarida inson obraziga davr ruhi — mehnat, fidoyilik, ijtimoiy mas'uliyat singari g'oyalar singdirilgan. Obraz zamon bilan yashaydi, o'zgaradi va bu o'zgarish o'quvchi tomonidan seziladi.

Adib timsollarni tarixiy kontekstda berarkan, ularni to'g'ridan-to'g'ri siyosiy yoki sotsial ifoda emas, balki hayotiy-realistik uslubda tasvirlaydi. Bu esa obrazning badiiy ishonchliligini oshiradi.

G'afur G'ulom obraz yaratishda badiiy ironiyadan ham mohirlik bilan foydalangan. U ba'zan kinoyali ohangda lirik qahramon yoki voqea-hodisaning ichki mohiyatini ochadi. Bu holat "Shum bola" asarida, ayniqsa, yaqqol seziladi — bolaning sho'xligi aslida hayotdagi adolatsizlik va bolalarcha qarashlar bilan uyg'unlashadi.

Ironiya orqali yaratilgan obrazlar ikki darajali talqinga ega bo'ladi: tashqi oddiylik ortida chuqur ma'no yashiringan. Bu uslubiy jihat adib obrazlarining zamonaviy adabiy tafakkur bilan uyg'unligidan dalolat beradi [5].

G'afur G'ulom lirikasi va ayrim nasriy asarlarida qahramonning ichki monologi obrazni psixologik jihatdan yanada chuqurlashtiradi. Ayniqsa, "Ona", "Yulduzim" kabi she'rlarda lirik qahramonning ichki so'zlari — iztirob, armon, umid, sog'inch orqali ifodalanadi. Bu obrazlar o'quvchi bilan bevosita hissiy aloqa o'rnatadi.

Monolog orqali berilgan obrazlar o'zini o'zi tahlil qiladi, savollar beradi, inkor qiladi va e'tirof etadi. Bu esa obrazga jonli, harakatdagi psixologik tabiat beradi. G'afur G'ulom aynan shu jihatlari orqali o'z obrazlarini faqat poetik emas, balki falsafiy-estetik darajaga olib chiqadi.

Xulosa va munozara. G'afur G'ulom ijodi obraz yaratishning yangi badiiy usullarini o'zida mujassamlashtirgan maktabdir. Uning obrazlari real hayotdan olingan bo'lsa-da, chuqur falsafiy va ruhiy qatlamlarga ega. Shoir inson qalbini, davr ruhini, ijtimoiy ziddiyatlarni poetik estetik vositalar orqali o'ziga xos tarzda aks ettiradi. G'afur G'ulom obrazlari milliy timsollarning zamonaviy talqini bo'lib, bugun ham o'z dolzarbligini yo'qotmagan. Aynan mana shunday obrazlar orqali shoir o'z asarlarini abadiy qildi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI:

1. G'afur G'ulom. Tanlangan asarlar. 1–2 jild. – Toshkent: G'afur G'ulom nomidagi NMIU, 2020.
2. "G'afur G'ulomning obraz yaratish mahorati" – Ilmiy maqola.
3. "G'afur G'ulom she'riyati va lirik qahramon ruhiyati tasviri" – Adabiy tahlil manbasi.
4. Qosimova G. O'zbek lirikasi poetikasi. – Toshkent: Fan, 2008.
5. Karimov O. Adabiy obraz va timsollar tahlili. – Toshkent: Akademiya nashri, 2019.

UDC 811

THE IMAGINATION AND INTERPRETATION OF WARRIORS IN HEROIC EPICS

E.N.Murtazayev, teacher, Asian Technological University, Qarshi

Annotatsiya. Maqolada xalq eposlarida urush va inson talqini, jangovar epizodlar tasvirining badiiy xususiyatlari tadqiq etilgan. "Alpomish" va "Odisseya" dostonlarining qiyosiy

tahlili asosida qahramonlik eposlarida ifodalangan urush voqeligining g'oyaviy asoslari o'rganilib, tahlillar ilmiy asosda dalillangan. Tahlillar davomida tegishli mavzuga doir ilmiy manbalardan foydalanilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: folklor, doston, obraz, talqin, "Alpomish", "Odisseya", sayyor syujet, qiyosiy usul.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается интерпретация войны и человечности в народном эпосе, а также художественные особенности изображения боевых эпизодов. На основе сравнительного анализа былин «Алпомиш» и «Одиссея» исследуются идеологические основы действительности войны, выраженные в героических эпосах, и дается научное обоснование анализа. При анализе использовались научные источники по соответствующей теме.

Ключевые слова: фольклор, эпос, образ, интерпретация, «Алпомиш», «Одиссея», странствующий сюжет, сравнительный метод.

Abstract. The article studies the artistic features of the depiction of war and humanity in folk epics, the depiction of combat episodes. Based on a comparative analysis of the epics "Alpomish" and "Odyssey", the ideological foundations of the reality of war expressed in heroic epics are studied, and the analyses are substantiated on a scientific basis. During the analysis, scientific sources on the relevant topic were used.

Keywords: folklore, epic, image, interpretation, "Alpomish", "Odyssey", itinerant plot, comparative method.

Introduction. Heroic epics first appeared in oral literature, where they reflected the processes of the emergence of various peoples and states, the processes of struggle between tribes and nationalities, and the courage of heroes who fought for the defense of the Fatherland. Images of war play an important role in such epics. It is the depiction of combat episodes and situations on the battlefield that make up a significant part of heroic epics, clearly expressing the character and unique features of the heroes. Also, heroic epics, regardless of the nationality they belong to, have many common features and similar aspects. The concept of "traveling plot" also applies, first of all, to folklore samples, and heroic epics are of particular importance in this regard. Also, folklore motifs migrated to the written epics of ancient times and were enriched with new features. The epics "Alpomish", which are examples of Uzbek folklore, and "Odyssey", created by the ancient Greek poet Homer based on the myths of the Trojan series, can serve as proof of the above ideas.

Material and methods. The epics "Alpomish" and "Odyssey" have always been in the focus of comparative scholars. In particular, such specialists as V. Zhirmunsky, V. Propp, K. Reichl, A. Abdurakhmonov, J. Eshonkul have studied the epics comparatively and analyzed their similarities and differences. Fozila Sulaymanova, who studied the relationship between ancient literature and ancient Central Asian culture, also considered the plot and artistic similarities of these epics [1, 40-98]. In general, these two epics serve as the main source for scientific discussions on the theory of "traveling plot", literary influence and typological similarities. In scientific discussions held to date, V. Zhirmunsky's interpretation remains the most complete. In his article "The Epic of Alpomish and Homer's Odyssey", the scientist concludes as follows about the epics: "The similarities between the examples of oral creativity are not the product of "literary influence", but the result of a common fairy tale plot widespread in ancient times" [2,332].

Results. As a result of a comparative analysis of the two epics, the commonality between such episodes as the main character's return to his homeland after a long captivity, his appearance as a savior by taking revenge on those who oppressed his relatives and people, and his arrival on his wife's wedding day is clearly visible. The epics also have common features such as the fact that the main character, upon returning to his homeland, is the first to go to his shepherd slaves, and the heroes are first recognized by their loyal animals. The similarities between the epics are associated with the closeness of artistic thinking between peoples and the commonality of values. These two epics have many common features in terms of plot, gallery of images, and depiction of various details. However,